

UNIVERSITY OF HARGEISA

COLLEGE OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Faculty of nutrition and food science

Title:

**Effect of maternal malnutrition on low birth weight at
Mohamed mooge MCH in hargeisasomaliland.**

**A thesis submitted to the University of Hargeisa, college of
Applied Science in partial fulfillment of the requirements for
the degree of nutrition and food Science.**

Supervisor:

Dr: Osman Mohamed Osman

July 5, 2022

Declaration A

“This Research titled **effect of maternal malnutrition on low birth weight at mohamedmooge MCH** is our original work and has not been presented for degree or any other academic award in any university or institution of learning.”

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Declaration B

“I confirm that the work reported in this thesis was carried out by the candidate under my supervision”

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Approval sheet

“I certify that this research report satisfies the partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the Bachelor Degree of Nutrition and food science at University of Hargeisa”

Supervisor:

Dr: Osman Mohamed Osman

Signature _____

July 5, 2022

Dedication

We dedicate this study to our lovely moms and fathers whom we will never be able to do anything without them. Our parent supports us for every step, every decision that we take, they let us to take our decision alone. we also dedicate it our beloved sister and brothers those who give us a support and help without any excuse, All of all Alhamdulillah for everything.

Also we dedicate our honorable students and Lecturers of Nutrition and food science. Special thanks also to our lecturers **Dr. Osman Mohamed Osman, Dr. Sacad Ahmed abdiwali and Mr. Hassan Hussein Nouh** who educated us the course of research methodology and taught us the SPSS program without their support, motivation and understanding we would never able to achieve our ambition.

Acknowledgement

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Secondly, we like to give blessing thanks to our parents for allowing us to realize our own potential. All the support, help and courage they have provided us over the years in our journey was the greatest gift anyone has ever given us. Unfortunately it is not possible to list all of them in this limited space but thanks to all of you for your help to complete this project.

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Abstract

Background: Low birth weight (LBW) is a global public health challenging problem. Its high priority stems from the fact that it is the major determinant of infant morbidity and that it contributes markedly to the overall burden of childhood death. It is a serious public health issue in the majority of African countries. Worldwide more than 20 million low birth weight occur annually with the incidence of 15 to 20%, majority of this occur in low- and middle-income countries and 95.6% occur in developing nations. Its regional estimate was 28% in South Asia, 13% in sub-Saharan Africa and 13% in least developed country, As EDHS 2011 report in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia 11.4% are low birth weight (LBW).

General objective of the study: To assess effect maternal malnutrition on low birth weight at Mohamed mooge MCH, hargeisasomaliland.

Methodology:

3.1 Research design

The design suitable for this type of study will be descriptive cross-sectional study design. So, this cross-sectional study design was conducted to effect of maternal malnutrition on low birth weight at Mohamed Mooge MCH in Hargeisa, somaliland.

Findings: the study clarifies that 9(17.3%) of the respondents were Male, and 43 (82.7%) of the respondents were Female. it also shows that 23 (44.2%) of the respondents were aged between 15-25 years, another 19(36.5%) of the respondents were aged between 26-35 years, while 9(17.3%) of the respondents were aged between 36-45 years and 1(1.9%) of the respondents was aged between 46 and above years.

Conclusion: level of maternal malnutrition at Mohamed mooge MCH indicates that they had a poor (medium) level of maternal malnutrition about which counts 38.5% and level of low birth weight at Mohamed mooge MCH was medium level as it is shown in the data which totals 31%.

Recommendation: In order mothers avoid themselves from malnutrition they should regularly do antenatal checkups and visit doctor during her pregnancy and after pregnancy as well, to early detect and treat any health conditions.

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List of Abbreviations

LBW: Low Birth Weight

VLBW: Very Low Birth Weight

ELBW: Extreme Low Birth Weight

IUGR: Intrauterine Growth Retardation

AGA: Appropriate For Gestational Age

SGA: Small for Gestational Age

WHO: World Health Organization

BMI: Body Mass Index

IUFD: Intrauterine Fetal Death

MCH: Maternal and Child Health

ANC: Antenatal Care

PNC: Postnatal Care

HC: Health Center

LMICS: Low and Middle Income Countries

1. Chapter one

1.1. Background of the study

Low birth weight (LBW) is a global public health challenging problem. Its high priority stems from the fact that it is the major determinant of infant morbidity and that it contributes markedly to the overall burden of childhood death. It is a serious public health issue in the majority of African countries. Low birth weight babies are in greatest risk during their early childhood. Birth weight below 2.5 kg reflects intrauterine malnutrition involving micro nutrients deficiencies and maternal malnutrition. The incidence of low birth weight is powerful indicator of infant's survival, and indirectly influences maternal nutritional status.

Globally, WHO estimates that 20 million low birth weights occur annually with the incidence of 15 to 20% majority of this occur in low- and middle-income countries and 95.6% occur in developing nations. Its regional estimate was 28% in South Asia, 13% in sub-Saharan Africa and 13% in least developed country, As EDHS 2011 report in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia 11.4% are low birth weight (LBW).(1)

In South Asia the incidence of LBW is 36%, 30% in Bangladesh and India, and 19% in Pakistan. In Pakistan the LBW rate varies from 5% to 23% in different parts, whilst IUGR in a community-based study in Karachi was found to be 24.4%(2). In Africa, prevalence of LBW was 9.47%, with variations among African regions ranged from 8.9% in eastern Africa to 10.3% in Southern Africa. selected African countries such as Burkina Faso, Ghana, Malawi, Senegal, and Uganda was, respectively, 13.4%, 10.2%, 12.1%, 15.7% and 10% [22], and systematic and meta-analysis results in Ethiopia (18%)(3).According to the latest WHO data published in 2017 low birth weight deaths in Somalia reached 4.954 or 3.94% of total deaths the age adjusted death rate is 22.27%per 100,000 of population ranks Somalia 19 in

the world recent other causes of death by low birth weight, malnutrition, maternal conditions (6).

Multiple risk factors associated with LBW include maternal age, socioeconomic characteristics, and nutritional status before and during pregnancy. Maternal undernutrition, including macronutrient and micronutrient deficiencies, is causally linked with LBW. The majority of LBW in low income and high income countries is due to intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR). The causes of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) include, poor nutritional status of the mother at conception, low weight gain during pregnancy due to insufficient dietary intake or extra expenditure of calories (hard work), short maternal height due to youthful under-nutrition and infections, anemia, acute and chronic infections that could result in under-nutrition and consecutive poor pregnancy outcomes including low birth weight (LBW). Poor **Maternal nutrition status** is one of the most important risk factors for low birth weight, preterm birth (<37 weeks) and intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), which are risk factors for increased morbidity and mortality in newborn infants.(5)

Therefore, in order to prevent and prevent this problem of low birth weight should be carried out awareness of pregnant mothers in rural to urban areas. Mothers should be advised to stay connected to health facilities as well as pregnant and lactating mothers should stay connected and receive maternal and child health services including antenatal care and postnatal care. The mother should be kept nutritious before and during pregnancy by giving or advising with a balanced diet.

1.2. Problem statement

Worldwide due to excellent antenatal care coverage and sophisticated health service every pregnant mother will attend antenatal care. In addition to all the essential nutrients provided during pregnancy to mothers. It is also

recommended to eat healthy foods during pregnancy and those she avoids, which risk both her health and the baby, This improves the nutrition of the expectant mother and the health of the fetus, because the fetus' nutritional value depends on the nutrition of the mother. Therefore the higher the mother's nutritional value the lower the risk of low birth weight.

In Somaliland, there is poor antenatal care, most of the people are nomads and this means they do not have access to health services because they do not have the money, this means they do not get the nutrients for maternity and this increases the weight of low birth weight. According to Somaliland demographic health survey 2020 (SLDHS 2020) 52 percent of women did not receive antenatal care (ANC), also 6% of pregnant women have a BMI of less than 17. Every pregnant mother with a low BMI gives birth to a low birth weight which increases infant mortality (4).

Therefore, this topic will see through effect of maternal malnutrition on low birth weight at mohamedmooge MCH, hargeisasomaliland

1.3. General objective

The main objective is to assess effect maternal malnutrition on low birth weight at Mohamed mooge MCH, hargeisasomaliland.

1.3.1. Specific objectives

- To determine socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents.
- To determine level of maternal mal nutrition at Mohamed Mooge MCH.
- To determine level of low birth weight at Mohamed Mooge MCH.
- To figure out effect of maternal malnutrition on low birth weight at Mohamed Mooge MCH

1.3.2. Research Questions

- What are socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents?

- What is level of maternal malnutrition at Mohamed Mooge MCH?
- What is the level of low birth weight in MCH Mohamed Mooge MCH?
- What is the effect of maternal malnutrition on low birth weight at Mohamed Mooge MCH

1.4. Significance of Study

This study will be useful in academic centers, especially in my country and it will equip the readers with fairly detailed information about low birth weight. Also, this study will be useful in government specially minister of Health (MOH) and Non-governmental organization (NGO) to use it as future plans or present issue of low birth weight. The University of Hargeisa will also benefit from this research, It will help University students to make reference when writing related studies on low birth weight and maternal malnutrition. On the other hand, the study will be useful to health professionals to achieve solution and to enhance the health care in baby who are suffering from low birth weight. Lastly this research will help the community and will increase comprehension about this low birth weight and how they will protect themselves from this problem.

1.5. Scope of the study

1.5.1. Geographical study

Somaliland officially the Republic of Somaliland is a self-declared state internationally recognized as an autonomous region in Somalia. It has hundreds of miles of coastline along the Gulf of Aden to the north, and it borders Ethiopia to the south and west and Djibouti to the northwest. It lies between Latitudes 8° and 11° 27' North and Longitudes 42° 35' and 49° East; it has mountain ranges rising up to six and seven thousand feet in the Centre and in the east of the country respectively. The total area of the Republic of Somaliland is 137, 600sqkms, and it has a coastline which is 850kms long.

Hargeisa is a city in the Marodijeh region of Somaliland in the Horn of Africa. It is the capital and largest city of Somaliland. The city has a fairly equable climate, and Hargeisa was originally the summer capital of former British Somaliland, of which it became the permanent administrative Centre in 1941. No large industries developed, but the city became an important watering and trading locus for the nomadic stock herders who formed the majority of the population. Meat, livestock, skins, and ghee are exported through Berbera, 117 miles (188 km) northeast, on the Gulf of Aden.

This research will be conducted from Mohamed mooge MCH. mohamedmoogemch is a MCH located in mohamedmooge district which is one of the districts of hargeisa, the capital of Somaliland. Mohamed mooge MCH programs focus on health issues concerning women, children and families, such as access to recommended prenatal antenatal, and well-child care, infant and maternal mortality prevention, maternal and child mental health, newborn screening, child immunizations, child nutrition and services for children with special health care needs. States invest in healthy children and families to strengthen communities and avoid unnecessary health care costs.

1.5.2. Time scope

The duration of study was from February to June 2022.

1.6. Operational terms of key terms

- **low birth weight (LBW):** Low birth weight has been defined by world health organization (WHO) as birth weight less than 2500g (5.5 pounds) this is based on epidemiological observation that infants weighting less than 2500g are 20 times to die then heavier babies more common in developing counties then developed countries birth weight less than 2500g contributes to range of poor health outcome.

- **Preterm birth:**Preterm birth is when a baby is born too early, before 37 weeks of pregnancy have been completed.
- **Intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR):**Intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) refers to the poor growth of a baby while in the mother's womb during pregnancy.
- **Maternal nutrition:** Maternal nutrition refers to the nutritional needs of women during antenatal and postnatal periods and sometimes also to the period prior to conception
- **Malnutrition:**Malnutrition refers to deficiencies, excesses, or imbalances in a person's intake of energy and/or nutrients
- **Antenatal care:** **Antenatal care** is the care you get from health professionals during your pregnancy. It's sometimes called pregnancy care or maternity care.

1.7. Conceptual frame work

2. Chapter two: literature review

2.1. Introduction:

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), low birth weight (LBW) is defined as the first weight after birth which is less than 2500 g (5.5 pounds), resulting from preterm birth (birth before 37 completed weeks) or due to intrauterine growth restriction or from both. Birth weight not only predicts the health status of the mother but also gives future information about the survival, development, and long-term health of the baby. Low birth weight is one of the important primary determinant and contributor to neonatal and infant mortality that contributes for nearly half of all prenatal and one-third of all infant deaths. Low birth weight babies have 40 times more chances to die within the first 30 days of life as compared to those with normal birth weight (NBW). So considering its importance, Low birth weight has been used as an important health indicator of a public health problem as per directives of WHO, because it reflects the malnutrition and metabolic conditions of the mother, as well as poor health care at population level during pregnancy, hence, it is the strongest predictor of newborn health and survival.

Developing countries of the world have been facing a very high burden of this condition with a 16.5% frequency of LBW, in comparison to developed countries (7%). Specifically, a condition in South Asia is worse due to low socioeconomic status (SES), and poor health care during pregnancy; as the global estimate is 18 million babies born per year with LBW and 9.3 million (50% of total) of them belong to South Asia. However, Pakistan has made some progress in achieving Millennium Development Goals with a frequency of 12%-25%, specifically in Lahore 21%, and in Karachi 29% babies born with LBW by the year 2017 and 2018, respectively

As we know, the nutritional needs during pregnancy are higher than usual days of life, and proper balance with extra nutrients can help both mother and

fetus in protecting long-term health outcomes. Many physiological modifications in mother, as well as the growth of fetus, increase the metabolic demand, and inadequate maternal nutritional status showed adverse pregnancy outcomes, poor infant survival, and impaired intellectual development in the coming life. Previous studies showed that the women who had consumed junk food, imbalanced diet, consumed less quantity of food, or those who escape meals during the first eight-week period of pregnancy are more prone to maternal mortality as well as fetal morbidity and mortality as compared to those who took healthily and enough quantity of meals. Hence, it is postulated that a well-fed mother gives birth to a healthy and normal weight child because they had a more favorable intrauterine environment.

There are many risk factors, for LBW including poor maternal nutrition and lifestyle factors such as the use of alcohol, smoking and tobacco; anemia, primiparity, low SES, mental stress during pregnancy, abuse in the family, lack of antenatal visits, short maternal height, and low maternal weight. Maternal health and nutritional status are modifiable risk factors that are particularly crucial in determining infant birth weight. The intake of sufficient energy, protein, and nutrients to meet maternal and fetal requirements is required for optimal growth and birth weight, low nutritional diet, and inadequate weight gain during pregnancy contribute to fewer nutrients that are required for fetal growth, such as vitamins and iron. Iron promotes the formation of new hemoglobin (Hb) and is responsible for an adequate supply of energy and oxygen to body organs. Maternal anemia can develop when Hb levels drop below 11 g/dL, which may lead to the unavailability of iron in an extracellular environment for erythropoiesis.

2.2. Theoretical perspective of the study

The general susceptibility approach could therefore be complementary to both germ theory and the multi-causal model of disease causation in health

promotion and disease prevention strategies at the population level given that it not only takes into account the multiple causes of disease, but also examines their distributions at sub-population levels. The process of disease causation is much more complex than a single causal factor to be explained by the germ theory of disease. The decline of mortality with the improved living conditions and public health suggests that disease causation is a complex development, involving a disease agent, a human host and the environment (both social and physical) that need to be understood as a multi-causal process. The disease agents are biological, chemical or physical factors, the presence of which is necessary to cause a disease. The human host, whose personal behaviors, genetic predisposition, immune system, and the emotional state make the person susceptible to the effect of the disease agent. The environment, which is external to the host, contributes either to weaken or to strengthen the host by the societal activities. The multicausality model emphasized the mediating social and physical environment, and the psychosomatic self-reported physical health status during the initial study in 1965, socio-economic status, and health practices, such as smoking, alcohol consumption, obesity, physical activity, and utilization of preventive health services will contribute to development of diseases this is supports my study because it emphases is that disease is caused by multiple causes and the cause of disease is always complex.

2.3. Empirical theory

2.3.1. Level of maternal malnutrition

Maternal nutrition refers to the nutritional needs of women during antenatal and postnatal periods and sometimes also to the period prior to conception. Maternal undernutrition is defined as having a body mass index of <18.5. maternal undernutrition is an important contributor to morbidity, mortality, and poor birth outcomes including low birth weight.

cross-sectional study published by Mohammed Muze, Mubarek Yesse, ShemsuKedir and AbdilmejidMustefa in southern Ethiopia on 19 November 2020. Stated that the prevalence of undernutrition among pregnant women was 21.8% current estimate is lower than previously reported in the study area, but higher than reported in developed countries. Age of the women, their birth interval, dietary change as a result of current pregnancy, and knowledge on nutrition were factors significantly associated with maternal undernutrition in the current study.

As well, systematic review of observational Published by Hanna DemelashDesyibelew and Abel FekaduDadi in Africa on September 6, 2019. shows that The rate of maternal malnutrition among pregnant women in Africa was reported as 16.6% in previous review while we found 23.5% in our current review and both estimates exceed 10%, which is a cut-off score for declaring maternal malnutrition as a major public health problem.

2.3.2. Level of low birth weight

Birth weight is strongly associated with infant morbidity and mortality, and is considered a predictor of immediate and future health status in newborns. Low birth weight, defined as less than 2500 g, may be a consequence of poor maternal nutrition poverty or associated with medical conditions, or a combination thereof.

A systemic review and meta-analysis study published by **NuradinAbushaKatiso**,GetachewMulluKassa,GedefawAbejeFekadu, AbadiK idanemariamBerhe,and AchenefAsmamawMuchein Ethiopia on 15 Sep 2020. stated that found a higher prevalence of low birth weight in Ethiopia,with high variation across the different regions in the country. The prevalence was 14.1%. A variety of differences in the prevalence of LBW between the different regions in Ethiopia was found. A higher prevalence of LBW (15.4%)

was seen in Tigray region, while the lowest (8.66%) was in Addis Ababa, Capital city of Ethiopia.

An Identical cross-sectional study determined by ZhifeiHe, GhoseBishwajit, Sanni Yaya, Zhaohui Cheng, Dongsheng Zou, and Yan Zhou in five Sub-Saharan countries: Burkina Faso, Ghana, Malawi, Senegal and Uganda on August 29, 2018. exposed that The prevalence of LBW ranged from 10% in Uganda to 15.7% in Senegal. Besides the intercountry differences, the prevalence of LBW varied within countries as well, with the prevalence being higher in rural women compared with urban women. The likelihood of having LBW babies was higher among women with lower parity, attending less than four ANC visits and who reported the last pregnancy as unintended.

Another cross-sectional study described by Henry BankoleOladeinde, OladapoBabatundeOladeinde, Richard Omoregie, and AdekunleAbdufattaiOnifade in nigeria on 2015 Dec. exhibited that the prevalence of low birth weight (LBW) in this study was 6.3% and was significantly affected by maternal age, maternal height, maternal anaemia, marital status, maternal nutrition.

2.3.3. Effect of maternal nutrition on low birth weight

Undernutrition during pregnancy physiologically demanding period would result in adverse pregnancy outcomes. Undernutrition makes the women more susceptible to diseases, more risk of having miscarriages, and gives birth to low weight baby whose survival is at risk. Nutritional status during pregnancy is directly linked to intrauterine growth retardation (IUGR) and birth weight. Babies with fetal growth restriction are at increased risk of death throughout infancy.

The cross-sectional study published byAmitava Pal, Sourav Manna, Balaram Das & Prakash C. Dhara in india on 1september 2020. Showed that various socio-demographic, maternal, and household environmental variables were

risk factors for LBW, poor economy, low socioeconomic status, and poor sanitation were identified as risk factors for LBW. Absence in ANC follow-up, teenage pregnancy, maternal low weight, and short height, not consuming additional diet and iron folic acid tablet, and multi-parity were identified as risk factors for LBW. Maternal undernutrition, anemia, hypertension, and history of chronic medical illness have increased the risk of LBW baby.

A homogenous cross-sectional study assessed by GashawGaredewWoldeamanuel, TeshomeGensaGeta, TesfayePetros Mohammed, MulualemBelachewShuba, and TemesgenAbera in Ethiopia on January 29, 2019, shown that nutritional status of pregnant women as indicated by maternal anthropometry and biochemical profile was associated with birth weight of the baby. Baby born to poorly nourished mother has a lower body weight as compared to the baby of better nourished mothers. Hence, the pregnant mother's diet must contain adequate and balanced nutrients to decrease the percentage of LBW babies. Therefore, different strategies such as intensive health education should be planned and carried out to improve the nutritional status of the pregnant women and to reduce the risk of LBW.

3. Chapter three: Research methodology

3.1. Introduction

This chapter is about the methods that were used for collecting information in this field. It mainly explains how this study was conducted.

As it is indicated in the title, this chapter includes the research methodology of the dissertation. In more details, in this part it outlines the research design, the research method, the research approach, and the methods of data collection.

It also focuses on the selection of the sample and sampling procedure, the target population, the validity and reliability of the study, administration of survey instrument, the type of data analysis, the ethical considerations and the research limitations of the project.

3.2. Research design

The design suitable for this type of study will be descriptive cross-sectional study design. So, this cross-sectional study design was conducted to effect of maternal malnutrition on low birth weight at Mohamed Mooge MCH in Hargeisa, somaliland.

The cross-sectional study design is deemed to be appropriate since it measures or estimates the variable attribute of the target population at a particular point in time. The choice for the descriptive cross-sectional study design was informed by the aim to determine the level of low birth weight, level of maternal malnutrition and effect of maternal malnutrition on low birth weight in the target population and can usually be conducted relatively faster.

3.3. Research Population

The study population for this study were mohamedmooge MCH staffs and those patients 15 to 45 of age of reproductive age who has sustained

malnutrition during their pregnancy and visited Mohamed Mooge MCH for medical care during the study period. The target population of this study was 60 people.

3.3.1. Inclusion criteria

The inclusion criteria for this study was be for staffs of Mohamed mooge MCH, women between the 15 to 45 of age of reproductive age and any relative in sufficient information on maternal malnutrition and low birth weight risk factors.

3.3.2. Exclusion criteria

Women less than reproductive age (15-45 age), and women greater than reproductive age(15-45 age) was excluded in this study.

3.4. Sample size

The sample size was used to achieve or attain the core objective of the study, the sample size of the respondents were determined using Slovan's sample selection formula which is:

$$\frac{n= N}{1+N(e^2)}$$

Where:

n = number of sample / sample size

N= the population size

E= the level of significance which is given (0.05) $e^2= (0.05)^2 = 0.0025$

$$\frac{n= 60}{1+60 (0.05)^2}$$

$$\frac{n= 60}{1+60(0.0025)}$$

n=60

1+0.15

n= 60

1.15

52 Respondents

3.5. Sampling technique

This research is probability method particularly Simple Random Sampling, because it can allow all members of research population to have an equal chance of being selecting for the sample and to avoid bias and others related errors.

3.6. Research area

The study was conducted in Mohamed Mooge MCH at Mohamed Mooge district, Hargeisa, Somaliland.

3.7. Data collection methods

Data sources were primary data, where data collection was quantitative method by conducting questionnaires, including questions about Socio-demographics, maternal malnutrition and low birth weight.

Before filling the questionnaires, the researchers introduced themselves to each participant and gave details about the topic and purpose of the study. Upon seeking consent to conduct the study, a questions asked to the students. A structured questionnaire were used to collect data and consisted of four parts, namely, socio-demographic factors, maternal malnutrition and low birth weight.

3.8. Data analysis

This research used descriptive statistics to analyze data using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version (20) as well as Microsoft excel. Information that was obtained from the questionnaires was checked, verified and entered computer. The analyzed data was presented in tables and graphs by using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) as well as Microsoft excel.

Data analysis is a broad category which assists the researcher to check the limitations from the study and also increases the accurateness of the data from the different aspects.

3.9. Research instruments

The data was collected using one type of data gathering instruments which is self-administered questionnaire especially close ended questions, it's easy obtaining data from the respondents within a short period of time, the questionnaire was written in simple English language and the researcher facilitated explanation for some inquires raised during the self- administered Questionnaire to collect specific and general information about the maternal malnutrition and low birth weight.

3.10. Validity and reliability of the instrument

In order to achieve a reliable and good validity of data and quality of the instrument we requested to be checked by experienced person, data collectors was admonished to check each respondent's questions is she/he fully answered all of them.

Data collectors were given an enough time to collect data, respondents were promised to keep their privacy to avoid information bias. The validity of this instrument is checked more than once to be sure that this information is valid and it's reliable since it's repeated twice and checked by experienced researcher. The questionnaire test used this formula:

$$V=RQ/TQ*100$$

Where, V=Validity, RQ= Relevant questions, TQ= Total number of questions

$$\frac{15}{20} \times 100 = 75 \%$$

3.11. Ethical considerations

This research paper will be consistent to and conformed with to social morals, and contextual values. It is guaranteed to be solely used as an academic purpose. It also assures not be harmed to any person, institution and/or any nation.

4. Chapter four: Data Analysis presentation and Interpretation.

Table 4.1: Gender of the respondents

Table 4.1

	Frequency	Percent
Male	9	17.3
Female	43	82.7
Total	52	100.0

Table 4.1 clarifies that 9(17.3%) of the respondents were Male, and 43 (82.7%) of the respondents were Female. Thus this shows us that most of the respondents were female.

Source: Primary data, 2022

Table 4.2:Age of the respondents

Table 4.2

	Frequency	Percent
15-25	23	44.2
26-35	19	36.5
36-45	9	17.3
46 and above	1	1.9
Total	52	100.0

Table 4.2 shows that 23 (44.2%) of the respondents were aged between 15-25 years, another 19(36.5%) of the respondents were aged between 26-35 years, while 9(17.3%) of the respondents were aged between 36-45 years and 1(1.9%) of the respondents was aged between 46 and above years.

So, after we interpreted our questionnaire the analysis shows that the majority of the people who answered this question were aged between 15-25 years.

Source: primary data, 2022

Table 4.3:Marital status of the respondents

Table4.3

	Frequency	Percent
Single	12	23.1
Married	40	76.9
Total	52	100.0

Table 4.3 reveals that 12(23.1%) of the respondents were single, and 40(76.9%) of the respondents were married. However, this tells us that the majority of the respondents were married.

Source: primary data, 2022

Table 4.4:Education level of respondents

Table4.4

	Frequency	Percent
Primary	9	17.3
Secondary	8	15.4
University	19	36.5
Illiterate	16	30.8
Total	52	100.0

Table 4.4 shows that 9(17.3%) of the respondents were primary, 8(15.4%) of the respondents were secondary, while 19(36.5%) of the respondents were university and 16(30.8%) of the respondents were illiterate, this tells us that the majority of the respondents were university level in education.

Source: primary data, 2022

Table 4.5: occupation of the respondents

Table 4.5

	Frequency	Percent
Employee	15	28.8
health professional	15	28.8
house wife	17	32.7
Jobless	5	9.6
Total	52	100.0

Table 4.5 express that 15 (28.8%) of the respondents were employee, 15 (28.8%) of the respondents were health professional, while 17(32.7%) of the respondents were house wife and 5 (9.6%) of the respondents were jobless, this table shows us that most of the respondents were house wife.

Source: primary data, 2022

Figure 4.1: have you ever heard about maternal malnutrition?

Figure 4.1

Figure 4.1 reveals that 52(100%) of the respondents answered that they have heard about maternal malnutrition, whereas other choices were zero in frequency and as well as in percent. However this tells us that all the respondents heard about maternal malnutrition.

Source: primary data, 2022

Figure 4.2:if yes where did you hear first time?

Figure4.2

Figure 4.2 exhibits that 42(80.8%) of the respondent were Health center, 9(17.3%) of the respondents were Family, and 1(1.9%) of the respondents were other. So, this reveals that most of the respondents heard about maternal malnutrition on health center.

Source: primary data, 2022

Figure 4.3:what is the most common cause of maternal malnutrition during pregnancy?

Figure4.4

Figure 4.3 demonstrate that 34(65.4%) of the respondents responded that this maternal malnutrition is most common caused by poor diet intake, as well as

1(1.9%) of the respondents responded that the most common cause of maternal malnutrition is poor maternal health, while 15 (28.8) of the respondents responded that the most common cause of the maternal malnutrition is low socioeconomic and 2(3.8) of the respondents responded that this maternal malnutrition is most common caused by infections. However this tells us that the most common cause of maternal malnutrition is poor diet intake.

Source: primary data, 2022

Figure 4.4:what is the consequence of malnutrition during pregnancy?

Figure4.4

Figure 4.4 explain that 17(32.7%) of the respondents responded that consequence of malnutrition during pregnancy is low birth weight, Another 6 (11.5%) of the respondents responded intrauterine growth retardation and while 29(55.8%) of the respondents responded that the result of pregnancy malnutrition was anemia.

This figure 4.4 tells us that the majority of the respondents were answered anemia. **Source: primary data, 2022**

Figure 4.5:what is the risk factor of maternal malnutrition?

Figure4.5

Figure 4.5 illustrate that 4(7.7%) of the respondents answered that risk factor of maternal malnutrition is teenage mothers, in addition to 12 (23.1%) of the respondents responded underweight, while 3 (5.8%) of the respondents responded illiterate mothers and 8(15.4%) of the respondents says that risk factor of maternal malnutrition is lack of antenatal care, as well as 25(48.1%) of the respondents responded low income, also this tells us that the majority of the respondents were replied low income.

Source: primary data, 2022

Figure 4.6:what is the level of maternal malnutrition at mohamedmooge MCH?

Figure4.6

Figure 4.6 demonstrate that 7(13.5%) of the respondents answered that they had high level of maternal malnutrition, while 20(38.5%) of the respondents responded that they had a medium level of maternal malnutrition, Another 7(13.5%) of the respondents replied that they had a low level of maternal malnutrition, Whereas 18(34.6%) said that they didn't know how their level of maternal malnutrition, However, this tells us that the majority of the respondents were Medium in level of maternal malnutrition.

Source: primary data, 2022

Figure 4.7: Do health staffs explain the need of prenatal care to every mother that visits the MCH in order to prevent the risk of maternal malnutrition?

Figure4.7

Figure 4.7 show that 31(59.6%) of the respondents strongly agreed that health staffs explain the need of prenatal care to every mother that visits the MCH in order to prevent the risk of maternal malnutrition, at the same time 15(28.8%) of the respondents agreed, but 1(1.9%) of the respondents strongly disagreed and 5(9.6%) of the respondents disagreed.

As we can see from the figure 4.7 above, all the respondents were replied strongly agree.

Source: primary data, 2022

Figure 4.8: do you believe the low birth weight is the result of maternal malnutrition?

Figure4.8

Figure 4.8 indicates that 98% of the respondents answered that they believe the low birth weight is the result of maternal malnutrition, whereas other choice were zero in frequency and as well as in percent.

However this tells us that all the respondents believes the low birth is the result of maternal malnutrition.

Source: primary data, 2022

Figure 4.9:what is the consequence of low birth weight?

Figure4.9

Figure 4.9clarifies that 29% of the respondents were replied that consequence of low birth weight is low oxygen levels at birth, whereas 15% of the

respondents answered inability to maintain body temperature while 33% of the respondents responded growth failure and another 23% were says that consequence of the low birth weight is death.

So, after we interpreted our questionnaire the analysis shows that the majority of the people were answered that the consequence of the low birth weight is growth failure.

Source: primary data, 2022

Figure 4.10:who is most affected by low birth weight?

Figure4.10

Figure 4.10 that 10% of the respondents responded that the most affected by low birth weight are teenage mothers, another 23% of the respondents were answered multiple birth, while 67% of the respondents says that the most affected by low birth weight is malnourished mother.

Therefore, this figure shows us that most of the respondents were replied that the most affected by low birth weight is mal nourished mother.

Source: primary data, 2022

Figure 4.11:the low birth weight is more risk to die according normal birth weight?

Figure4.11

Figure 4.11 shows that 34% of the respondents were answered that low birth weight is not more to die than normal birth weight, while 66% of the respondents replied that low birth weight is more risk to die according normal birth weight.

Hence, this tells us the majority of the respondents were responded yes.

Source: primary data, 2022

Figure 4.12:what is the type of low birth weight do you meet?

Figure4.12

figure 4.12 indicates that 27% of the respondents says that type of low birth weight they meet is the low birth weight LBW, while 15% of the respondents responded very low birth weight VLBW, whereas 21% of the respondents replied Extreme low birth weight ELBW and 37% of the respondents were answered that they don't meet .

Also, this figure above shows us that most of the respondents were responded that they don't meet.

Source: primary data, 2022

Figure 4.13: what is the level of low birth weight at mohamedmooge MCH?

Figure4.13

Figure 4.13 shows that 8% of the respondents answered that they had high level of low birth weight, while 31% of the respondents responded that they had a medium level of low birth weight, Another 19% of the respondents replied that they had a low level of low birth weight, Whereas 42% said that they didn't know how their level of low birth weight is.

However, this tells us that the majority of the respondents were replied that they didn't know how their level of low birth weight is.

Source: primary data, 2022

Figure 4.14:Malnutrition during pregnancy has an impact on the pregnancy's outcome and can lead to complications like low birth weight, which has a negative impact on the baby's life?

Figure4.14

Figure 4.14 show that 75% of the respondents strongly agreed that Malnutrition during pregnancy has an impact on the pregnancy's outcome and can lead to complications like low birth weight, which has a negative impact on the baby's life, while 21% of the respondents agreed, but 2% of the respondents strongly disagreed and 2% of the respondents disagreed.

As we can see from the figure 4.14 above, 75% the respondents were replied strongly agree.

Source: primary data, 2022

Figure 4.15:Do mothers believe that malnutrition during pregnancy affects the fetus' weight?

Figure4.15

Figure 4.15 reveals that 83%) of the respondents answered that they believe that malnutrition during pregnancy affects the fetus' weight, whereas other choices were zero in frequency and as well as in percent.

However this tells us that all the respondents they believe that malnutrition during pregnancy affects the fetus' weight.

Source: primary data, 2022.

5. CHAPTER FIVE: FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1. Introduction

This chapter contains three sections; discussion of the findings, conclusion and recommendation. This study was intended to explore the effect of maternal malnutrition on low birth weight at Mohamed mooge MCH.

5.2. Discussion of the findings

5.2.1 Demographic findings of the research population

Table 4.1 clarifies that 9(17.3%) of the respondents were Male, and 43 (82.7%) of the respondents were Female.

Thus this shows us that most of the respondents were female.

Table 4.2 shows that 23 (44.2%) of the respondents were aged between 15-25 years, another 19(36.5%) of the respondents were aged between 26-35 years, while 9(17.3%) of the respondents were aged between 36-45 years and 1(1.9%) of the respondents was aged between 46 and above years.

So, after we interpreted our questionnaire the analysis shows that the majority of the people who answered this question were aged between 15-25 years.

Table 4.3 reveals that 12(23.1%) of the respondents were single, and 40(76.9%) of the respondents were married.

However, this tells us that the majority of the respondents were married.

Table 4.4 shows that 9(17.3%) of the respondents were primary, 8(15.4%) of the respondents were secondary, while 19(36.5%) of the respondents were university and 16(30.8%) of the respondents were illiterate.

This tells us that the majority of the respondents were university level in education.

Table 4.5 express that 15 (28.8%) of the respondents were employee, 15 (28.8%) of the respondents were health professional, while 17(32.7%) of the respondents were house wife and 5 (9.6%) of the respondents were jobless.

This table shows us that most of the respondents were house wife.

5.2.2 Questions related to maternal malnutrition, low birth weight and effect of maternal malnutrition on low birth weight at Mohamed mooge MCH.

Figure 4.1 reveals that 52(100%) of the respondents answered that they have heard about maternal malnutrition, whereas other choices were zero in frequency and as well as in percent.

However this tells us that all the respondents heard about maternal malnutrition.

Figure 4.2 exhibits that 42(80.8%) of the respondent were Health center, 9(17.3%) of the respondents were Family, and 1(1.9%) of the respondents were other.

So, this reveals that most of the respondents heard about maternal malnutrition on health center.

Figure 4.3 demonstrate that 34(65.4%) of the respondents responded that this maternal malnutrition is most common caused by poor diet intake, as well as 1(1.9%) of the respondents responded that the most common cause of maternal malnutrition is poor maternal health, while 15 (28.8) of the respondents responded that the most common cause of the maternal malnutrition is low socioeconomic and 2(3.8) of the respondents responded that this maternal malnutrition is most common caused by infections.

However this tells us that the most common cause of maternal malnutrition is poor diet intake.

Figure 4.4 explain that 17(32.7%) of the respondents responded that consequence of malnutrition during pregnancy is low birth weight, Another 6 (11.5%) of the respondents responded intrauterine growth retardation and while 29(55.8%) of the respondents responded that the result of pregnancy malnutrition was anemia.

Therefore, tells us that the majority of the respondents were answered anemia.

Figure 4.5 illustrate that 4(7.7%) of the respondents answered that risk factor of maternal malnutrition is teenage mothers, in addition to 12 (23.1%) of the respondents responded underweight, while 3 (5.8%) of the respondents responded illiterate mothers and 8(15.4%) of the respondents says that risk factor of maternal malnutrition is lack of antenatal care, as well as 25(48.1%) of the respondents responded low income.

So, this tells us that the majority of the respondents were replied low income.

Figure 4.6 demonstrate that 7(13.5%) of the respondents answered that they had high level of maternal malnutrition, while 20(38.5%) of the respondents responded that they had a medium level of maternal malnutrition, Another 7(13.5%) of the respondents replied that they had a low level of maternal malnutrition, Whereas 18(34.6%) said that they didn't know how their level of maternal malnutrition.

However, this tells us that the majority of the respondents were Medium in level of maternal malnutrition.

Figure 4.7 show that 31(59.6%) of the respondents strongly agreed that health staffs explain the need of prenatal care to every mother that visits the MCH in order to prevent the risk of maternal malnutrition, at the same time 15(28.8%) of the respondents agreed, but 1(1.9%) of the respondents strongly disagreed and 5(9.6%) of the respondents disagreed.

As we can see from the figure 4.7 above, all the respondents were replied strongly agree.

Figure 4.8 indicates that 98% of the respondents answered that they believe the low birth weight is the result of maternal malnutrition, whereas other choice were zero in frequency and as well as in percent.

However this tells us that all the respondents believes the low birth is the result of maternal malnutrition.

Figure 4.9clarifies that 29% of the respondents were replied that consequence of low birth weight is low oxygen levels at birth, whereas 15% of the respondents answered inability to maintain body temperature while 33% of the respondents responded growth failure and another 23% were says that consequence of the low birth weight is death.

So, after we interpreted our questionnaire the analysis shows that the majority of the people were answered that the consequence of the low birth weight is growth failure.

Figure 4.10 that 10% of the respondents responded that the most affected by low birth weight are teenage mothers, another 23% of the respondents were answered multiple birth, while 67% of the respondents says that the most affected by low birth weight is malnourished mother.

Therefore, this figure shows us that most of the respondents were replied that the most affected by low birth weight is mal nourished mother.

Figure 4.11 shows that 34% of the respondents were answered that low birth weight is not more to die than normal birth weight, while 66% of the respondents replied that low birth weight is more risk to die according normal birth weight.

Hence, this tells us the majority of the respondents were responded yes.

figure 4.12 indicates that 27% of the respondents says that type of low birth weight they meet is the low birth weight LBW, while 15% of the respondents responded very low birth weight VLBW, whereas 21% of the respondents replied Extreme low birth weight ELBW and 37% of the respondents were answered that they don't meet .

Also, this figure above shows us that most of the respondents were responded that they don't meet.

Figure 4.13 shows that 8% of the respondents answered that they had high level of low birth weight, while 31% of the respondents responded that they had a medium level of low birth weight, Another 19% of the respondents replied that they had a low level of low birth weight, Whereas 42% said that they didn't know how their level of low birth weight is.

However, this tells us that the majority of the respondents were replied that they didn't know how their level of low birth weight is.

Figure 4.14 show that 75% of the respondents strongly agreed that Malnutrition during pregnancy has an impact on the pregnancy's outcome and can lead to complications like low birth weight, which has a negative impact on the baby's life, while 21% of the respondents agreed, but 2% of the respondents strongly disagreed and 2% of the respondents disagreed.

As we can see from the figure 4.14 above, all the respondents were replied strongly agree.

5.3. Conclusion

5.3.1 Socio demographic characteristics:

To begin with the age of the respondent the majority age that participated the study was 15-25 years which accounts 44.2%). in addition to that gender perspective female accumulates largest part of study containing 82.7%. furthermore, most of the respondents were married 76.9%).however, regarding

educational level of the majority respondents 36.5% were university level in education. according to occupation level of the respondents 32.7% house wife.

5.3.2 Level of maternal malnutrition

To begin with the level of maternal malnutrition at Mohamed mooge MCH indicates that they had a poor (medium) level of maternal malnutrition about which counts 38.5%. cross-sectional study published by Mohammed Muze, MubarekYesse, ShemsuKedir and AbdilmejidMustefa in southern Ethiopia on 19 November 2020. Stated that the prevalence of undernutrition among pregnant women was 21.8% current estimate is lower than previously reported in the study area, but higher than reported in developed countries.

5.3.3 Level of low birth weight.

According to level of low birth weight at Mohamed mooge MCH was medium level as it is shown in the data which totals 31%. cross-sectional study described by Henry BankoleOladeinde, OladapoBabatundeOladeinde, Richard Omoregie, and AdekunleAbdufattaiOnifade in nigeria on 2015 Dec. exhibited that the prevalence of low birth weight (LBW) in this study was 6.3% and was significantly affected by maternal age, maternal height, maternal anaemia, maternal nutrition.

5.3.4 Effect of maternal malnutrition on low birth weight

Finally, this study found Malnutrition during pregnancy has an impact on the pregnancy's outcome and can lead to complications like low birth weight, which has a negative impact on the baby's life, because our data show that 75% of the respondents were responding strongly agree that pregnancy malnutrition affects fetal weight, as well as 83% of respondents also believe that fetal malnutrition affects the fetus.

5.4. Recommendation

- ✓ We recommend Further research on this topic
- ✓ Raising awareness on effect of maternal malnutrition on low birth weight
- ✓ Mothers should take healthy diet and as well as balanced ones. such as : milk , eggs , fiber , fruits and vegetables , drink more water , eat meals high in protein and iron .
- ✓ In order mothers avoid themselves from malnutrition they should regularly do antenatal checkups and visit doctor during her pregnancy and after pregnancy as well, to early detect and treat any health conditions that mother has and dietary treatments and recommendations from midwife or doctor of kind of food to eat and which meal is better during her pregnancy to increase the health of her unborn baby and good pregnancy outcomes and things to avoid during pregnancy such as doing heavy work , stressful situations that mother can face that can harm her baby , foods not to eat and avoid such as tea , coffee , high sugar beverages , high fat meals and foods that contain sodium in high amounts .
- ✓ Mothers should maintain their health and avoid any factors that influence their health and health of their baby and follow healthy habits during their pregnancy such as avoid drinking alcohol, chewing Kat, smoking cigarettes, eating non healthy foods, mothers should put their selves away from depression and stressful condition that can cause effect their pregnancy because these factors contribute to development of maternal malnutrition during pregnancy.

Appendix I

Reference

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Appendix II

QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear respondents,

We are Nasra, abshir, abdirahman and samiira. We are one of the senior nutrition students in university of Hargeisa, which will be graduating in this year. We are conducting a research on effect of maternal malnutrition on low birth weight at mohamedmooge MCH. We realize how precious your time is. That's why we made sure this survey will only take a quick amount of time, so please complete this short 3-minutes survey to let us know effect of maternal malnutrition on low birth weight at mohamedmooge MCH. All responses are recorded anonymously so feel free to provide honest feedback. Your responses will help us know a facts about the effect of maternal malnutrition and low birth weight.

Indeed, we would like to thank you for being one of the respondents who are selected to complete this survey.

Section one: Demographic Characteristics

1. What is your gender?
A. Male B. female
2. What is your age?
A. 15-25 B. 26-35 C. 36- 45 D.46 and above
3. What is your marital status?
A. Single B. Married orce Widow
4. What is your level of education?
A. Primary B. Secondary C. University D. illiterate
5. What is your occupational level?
A. Employee B. Health professional C. House wife
D. jobless

Section two: maternal malnutrition.

6. Have you ever heard about maternal malnutrition?
A. Yes
B. No

7. If yes, where did you hear first time?
 - A. Health center
 - B. Family
 - C. Social media
 - D. Other
8. What is the most common cause of maternal malnutrition during pregnancy?
 - A. Poor diet intake.
 - B. Poor maternal health
 - C. low socioeconomic status
 - D. infections
9. What is the consequence of malnutrition during pregnancy?
 - A. Anemia
 - B. Intrauterine growth retardation.
 - C. low birth weight
 - D. miscarriage
10. what is the risk factor of maternal malnutrition?
 - A. Teen age mothers (especially those younger than 15 years old)
 - B. Under weight
 - C. Illiterate mother
 - D. Lack of antenatal care
 - E. Low income
11. What is the level of maternal malnutrition at Mohamed mooge MCH?
 - A. High
 - B. Medium
 - C. Low
 - D. I don't know
12. Do health staffs explain the need of prenatal care to every mother that visits the MCH in order to prevent the risk of maternal malnutrition.
 - A. Strongly agree
 - B. Agree
 - C. Strongly disagree
 - D. Disagre

Section three: low birth weight.

13. Do you believe the low birth weight is the result of maternal malnutrition?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
14. What is the consequence of low birth weight?
 - A. Low oxygen levels at birth

- B. Inability to maintain body temperature
- C. Growth failure
- D. Death

15. Who is most affected by low birth weight?

- A. Teen age mothers (especially those younger than 15 years old) .
- B. Multiple birth.**
- C. Malnourished Mother.

16. The low birth weight is more risk to die according normal birth weight.

- A. Strongly agree
- B. Agree
- C. Strongly disagree
- D. Disagree

17. What is the most type of low birth weight do you meet?

- A. Low birth weight (<2.5 kg)
- B. Very low birth weight (<1.5 kg)
- C. Extreme low birth weight (<1kg)
- D. I don't know

18. What is the level of low birth weight (LBW) at Mohamed mooge MCH?

- E. High
- F. Medium
- G. Low
- H. I don't know

Section four: effect of maternal malnutrition on low birth weight.

19. Malnutrition during pregnancy has an impact on the pregnancy's outcome and can lead to complications like low birth weight, which has a negative impact on the baby's life.

- A. Strongly agree
- B. Agree
- C. Strongly disagree
- D. Disagree

20. Do mothers believe that malnutrition during pregnancy affects the fetus' weight?

- A. Strongly agree
- B. Agree

C. Strongly disagree

D. Disagree